

TO ESTIMATE GROWTH RATE IN AREA, PRODUCTION AND YIELD OF COTTON IN MARATHWADA REGION.

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Abstract

Cotton (*Gossypium spp*) the white gold is one of the most important cash crop in the world. although cotton is primary a fibre crop, it is also used as a food and feed crop. Cotton seed being the world`s second most oilseeds used for culinary purposes and the oil cake residue is a protein rich feed for ruminant livestock. Cotton play an important role in Indian economy as it contribute significantly to both agriculture and industry in terms of farm income employment and export earnings. On the acreage front, India is a world leader in term of area under cotton, account for about 24 per cent of the Total world area under cotton cultivation and 5 per cent of Total cultivated area in India. In terms of production, India ranks fourth in the world trailing behind China, Uzabikistan and USA. Maharastra is the largest cotton growing state in the country. It covers about 38 .06 lakh hectare area and is 1st in India followed by Gujarat. The total production and total productivity is 89 lakh bales and 396 kg/ha in 2016-17, respectively.

Keywords-Cotton, Employment and Export earning, Cotton cultivation, Total production and Total productivity.

Introduction:

Cotton (*Gossypium spp.*), the 'white gold' is one of the most important cash crop in the world. Cotton is primarily a fiber crop, it is also used as a food and feed crop. Cotton seed being the world's second most oilseeds used for culinary purposes and the oil cake residue is a protein rich feed for ruminant livestock.

Cotton plays an important role in Indian economy as it contribute significantly to both agriculture and industry in terms of farm income, employment, and export earnings. The cotton textile industry is the largest industry in India which accounts for 5 per cent of the total value of production in the organized manufacturing sector and about 10 per cent of country's total export earning. About 60 million people thrive on cotton cultivation, trade and processing. India has 1569 textile mills comprising 1295 s pinning and 274 composite mills. The textile industry generates employment for about 1.2 million people in the industry itself and nearly to 21 million people in the supporting industries. Employment generation for a large number of skilled, semiskilled and unskilled persons, particularly for low-income group at the village level, is the major strength of this industry.

Historically, India has been an exporter of raw cotton to the world. As early as 1800 AD, India exported 150 thousand bales of cotton. During 19th century, cotton cultivation in India expanded rapidly and covered almost 6 million bales of cotton lint. Although domestic demand was rising, still about two-thirds of the production found export outlets. Swadeshi movement during the early year of 20th century further helped cotton cultivation and by the end of 1920 cotton covered an area of 10 million hectares producing 5.5 million bales of which two thirds was exported.

Methodology

The present chapter deals with the concise description of the data required, its collection and analytical methods used in the light of stated objectives. The specific study was concern to the analysis of growth and instability of area, production and yield of cotton in Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state. The study also aims to find out the pace of growth of area, production and yield of cotton in different period and to find out the relative contribution of area and yield toward change in production over a period of time

Results and discussion

This chapter focuses results of the present study. The results of the study were analyzed with the use of basic data collected for present investigation. The data has been processed and tabulated in the light of the objectives of this study.

Secondly, the data was analysed and,Cuddy Della Vella instability index was calculated order to detect the instability in area, production and yield of cotton crops in different sub-periods and overall period of study for Marathwada region. Another important point of study was to calculate the growth rate in area, production and yield of cotton crops in two sub-periods of study. Finally, the contributions of various components of production viz. area, yield and their interaction effect towards change in cotton production were calculated.

The whole chapter was divided into following sub heads and overall study period.

To estimate growth rate in area production and yield of cotton in Marathwada region.

The growth in area, production and yield of cotton. were estimated using compound growth rates as indicated in methodology chapter. The general growth performance of cotton in all districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state was estimated and reported from table 1.1 to 1.3

Growth in cotton area in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state

The perusal of the table 1.1 revealed that, during all period, compound growth rates of cotton area were positive for all districts of Marathwada region. During period-I (1988-89 to 2001-02), the highest compound growth rate in area of cotton was registered in Beed district (12.05 per cent) followed by Aurangabad (10.09 per cent) and Jalna (3.24 per cent) districts. Almost all districts in Marathwada region has significant at 1 per cent except Parbhani district was significant at 5 per cent. The lowest positive compound growth rate in area of cotton was registered in Parbhani district 0.02 per cent per annum, which was found at Non significance. It was revealed that, during second period (2002-03 to 2015-16), picture drastically changed, the compound growth registered positive in all districts excep Latur district (-8.54 per cent). Highest compound growth rate of cotton was respected in Osmanabad i.e 23.47 followed by Beed and Aurangabad i.e 11.91 and 8.08. During overall period, all districts of Marathwada region have exhibited positive growth rate in area of cotton. Highest growth rate observed in Osmanabad district (22.41) followed by Beed (10.41 per cent) and Aurangabad (8.24 per cent). The area growth in cotton in all districts in Marathwada region were statistically significant at 1 per cent level of significance Except Hingoli and Parbhani i.e -0.51 and -0.96, respectively. The lowest positive compound growth rate in area of cotton was registered in Nanded district In the study of marketing of brinjal three marketing channels were identified channel-I producer-consumer, channel-II producer-retailer-consumer, and channel-III producer-commission agent cum wholesaler-retailer-consumer.

Table 1.1: Growth in cotton area in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state

Sr. No.	Name	Period-I		Period-II		Overall	
		CGR	't' value	CGR	't' value	CGR	't' value
01	Aurangabad	10.09	10.45**	8.08	14.85**	8.24	29.89**

		(0.96)		(0.54)		(0.27)	
02	Jalna	3.24 (0.42)	7.68**	5.35 (0.84)	6.34**	4.60 (0.30)	15.33**
03	Beed	12.05 (1.43)	8.41**	11.91 (0.85)	13.94**	10.41 (0.49)	21.20**
04	Latur	0.20 (0.90)	0.23 ^{NS}	-8.54 (2.29)	-3.73**	-6.23 (1.06)	-5.84**
05	Osmanabad	NA	NA	23.47 (3.70)	6.33**	22.41 (2.85)	7.84**
06	Nanded	1.79 (0.21)	8.37**	4.41 (0.39)	11.09**	1.14 (0.26)	4.33**
07	Parbhani	0.02 (0.74)	0.03 ^{NS}	3.41 (0.34)	9.84**	-0.96 (0.36)	-2.68*
08	Hingoli	NA	NA	2.51 (0.74)	3.35**	-0.51 (0.84)	-0.61 ^{NS}
09	Marathwada	3.60 (0.36)	9.85**	6.41 (0.26)	24.65**	3.88 (0.25)	15.19**
10	Maharashtra	1.93 (0.29)	6.63**	4.05 (0.30)	13.31**	1.76 (0.20)	8.62**

Note: Period-I: 1988-89 to 2001-02, Period-II: 2002-03 to 2015-16,, Overall Period: 1988-89 to 2015-16. Figures in bracket indicate standard error,* denotes significant at 5 percent, ** denotes significant at 1 percent, NS – Non Significant.

Growth in cotton production in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state

The district wise compound growth rate in production of cotton in Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state for two period and overall also worked out presented in table 1.2 The perusal of the table 1.2 revealed that, during period-I compound growth rates of cotton production were positive for all districts of Marathwada region. During period-I, the highest compound growth in production of cotton in Beed

district (12.59 per cent) followed by Jalna (6.64) and Aurangabad (5.38 per cent). All districts in Marathwada region which shows highly significant at 1 per cent except Latur district which statistically significant at 5 percent level. Under period-I, compound growth rates of production in Marathwada region and Maharashtra state was 4.99 and 4.17 per cent per annum which were found significant at 1 per cent level of significance.

Table 1.2: Growth in cotton production in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state

Sr. No.	Name	Period-I		Period-II		Overall	
		CGR	't' value	CGR	't' value	CGR	't' value
01	Aurangabad	5.38 (1.20)	4.46**	8.54 (2.39)	3.58**	10.46 (1.35)	7.74**
02	Jalna	6.64 (0.77)	8.63**	4.43 (2.43)	1.83 ^{NS}	7.42 (1.25)	5.93**
03	Beed	12.59 (1.69)	7.41**	10.24 (2.50)	4.09**	10.89 (1.24)	8.73**
04	Latur	3.26 (1.24)	2.62*	8.54 (3.37)	2.53*	-3.15 (1.05)	-3.00**
05	Osmanabad	NA	NA	21.13 (5.16)	4.09**	21.29 (4.01)	5.31**
06	Nanded	2.18 (1.02)	2.13 ^{NS}	8.41 (2.48)	3.38**	5.60 (0.90)	6.18**
07	Parbhani	2.58 (2.10)	1.23 ^{NS}	5.49 (1.66)	3.30**	4.38 (0.70)	6.20**
08	Hingoli	NA	NA	4.12 (1.97)	2.09 ^{NS}	4.67 (1.49)	3.13**
09	Marathwada	4.99 (0.97)	5.12**	7.06 (1.95)	3.62**	7.83 (0.87)	8.95**
10	Maharashtra	4.17 (0.91)	4.57**	6.72 (1.36)	4.92**	6.32 (0.55)	11.47**

Note: Period-I: 1988-89 to 2001-02, Period-II: 2002-03 to 2015-16,, Overall Period: 1988-89 to 2015-16. Figures in bracket indicate standard error,* denotes significant at 5 percent, ** denotes significant at 1 percent, NS – Non Significant.

Growth in cotton productivity in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state

It is revealed from the data in table 1.3 that, during period 1st (1988-89 to 2001-02) highest growth in productivity of cotton in Jalna district

was 3.48 per cent (with standard error 00.50). The lowest growth in cotton productivity in Beed district i.e. 1.24 per cent. Decline growth rate is Aurangabad district -4.10 per cent.

Table 1.3: Growth in cotton yield in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state

Sr. No.	Name	Period-I		Period-II		Overall	
		CGR	't' value	CGR	't' value	CGR	't' value
01	Aurangabad	-4.10 (0.74)	-5.48**	4.00 (2.11)	1.90 ^{NS}	3.35 (0.80)	4.18**
02	Jalna	3.48 (0.50)	6.87**	0.54 (1.56)	0.35 ^{NS}	4.00 (0.70)	5.66**

03	Beed	1.24 (0.53)	2.34*	2.06 (1.53)	1.35 ^{NS}	2.46 (0.45)	5.36**
04	Latur	2.80 (1.00)	2.79*	9.09 (2.51)	3.62**	7.41 (0.99)	7.48**
05	Osmanabad	NA	NA	5.15 (1.70)	3.01*	5.62 (1.13)	4.94**
06	Nanded	0.48 (1.11)	0.44 ^{NS}	4.59 (1.75)	2.62*	3.73 (0.62)	5.93**
07	Parbhani	2.50 (1.64)	1.53 ^{NS}	2.77 (1.66)	1.66 ^{NS}	4.77 (0.74)	6.41**
08	Hingoli	NA	NA	1.93 (1.92)	1.00 ^{NS}	3.99 (1.70)	2.34*
09	Marathwada	1.66 (0.95)	1.74 ^{NS}	2.57 (1.53)	1.67 ^{NS}	4.15 (0.62)	6.66**
10	Maharashtra	2.34 (0.91)	2.55*	3.41 (1.19)	2.85*	4.22 (0.47)	8.87**

Note: Period-I: 1988-89 to 2001-02, Period-II: 2002-03 to 2015-16,, Overall Period: 1988-89 to 2015-16. Figures in bracket indicate standard error,* denotes significant at 5 percent, ** denotes significant at 1 percent, NS – Non Significant.

Growth in cotton area in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state

The perusal of the table 1.4 revealed that, during all period, compound growth rates of cotton area were positive for all districts of Marathwada region. During period-I (1988-89 to 2001-02), the highest compound growth rate in area of cotton was registered in Beed district (12.05 per cent) followed by Aurangabad (10.09 per cent) and Jalna (3.24 per cent) districts. Almost all districts in Marathwada region has significant at 1 per cent except Parbhani district was significant at 5 per cent. The lowest positive compound growth rate in area of cotton was registered in Parbhani district 0.02 per cent per annum, which was found at Non significance. It was revealed that, during second period (2002-03 to 2015-16), picture drastically changed, the compound growth registered positive in all districts except Latur district (-8.54 per cent). Highest compound growth rate of cotton was respected in Osmanabad i.e 23.47 followed by Beed and Aurangabad i.e 11.91 and 8.08

During overall period, all districts of Marathwada region have exhibited positive growth rate in area of cotton. Highest growth rate observed in Osmanabad district (22.41) followed by Beed (10.41 per cent) and Aurangabad (8.24 per cent).The area growth in cotton in all districts in Marathwada region were statistically significant at 1 per cent level of significance Except Hingoli and Parbhani i.e -0.51 and -0.96, respectively. The lowest positive compound growth rate in area of cotton was registered in Nanded district

Conclusions

Maximum average productivity of cotton was recorded in Hingoli district i.e. 280 kg per hectare followed by Osmanabad and Aurangabad i.e. 201 and 194 kg per hectare, respectively. Lowest average productivity of cotton was in Nanded district (130 kg per hectare) followed by Parbhani and Beed district. It was 185 and 156 kg per hectare, respectively. It was observed that average productivity under cotton crop in Marathwada region during the first period, under study was 118 kg per hectare followed by 231 and 172 kg per hectare during second and overall period, respectively. Average productivity under cotton crop in Maharashtra state during the first period of study (1988-89 to 2001-02) was 131 hundred hectare during sub-sequent

period, it was 242 and 187 hundred hectare i.e. Second and overall period, respectively.

All districts of Marathwada region have exhibited positive growth rate in area of cotton. Highest growth rate was observed in Osmanabad district followed by Beed and Aurangabad .The area growth in cotton in all districts in Marathwada region were statistically significant at 1 per cent level of significance Except Hingoli and Parbhani. The lowest positive compound growth rate in area of cotton was registered in Nanded district which was found significant at 1 percent level of significance .Growth rate of cotton area in Marathwada region, during the first period of study was. 3.60 per cent, during sub-sequent period it was 6.41, and 3.88 per cent. Growth rate of cotton area in Maharashtra state during the first period under study was 1.93 per cent, during sub-sequent period it was 4.05, and 1.76 per cent i.e. Second and over all period, respectively.

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